

CLASSIFICATION OF MUSIC COMPUTER SOFTWARE

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The problems of improving the quality and effectiveness of musical education are of particular importance against the background of a serious decline in the spiritual and musical culture of students. Introducing modern information technologies into the educational process is one of the ways to activate the musical education of students. The use of information technologies in the higher education system has a significant impact on the quality of teaching various subjects, which allows teachers and students to "save time".

The abundance of various musical education, games and computer programs leads to the need to determine, first of all, the things that ensure the formation of students' interest in the art of music. To do this, it is possible to divide into the following classifications, which allows you to divide all music computer programs into the following groups:

- ❑ music players;
- ❑ programs for singing in karaoke;
- ❑ music editors;
- ❑ music encyclopedias;
- ❑ educational programs;
- ❑ programs for improvisation and musical compositions.

Below, each of these classification groups will be covered in detail, and we will provide the student with detailed information about each classification.

Music players. The most common types of this group are Windows Media Player, AIMP, WinAmp, JeAudio Plus and Groove music. The possibilities of these programs are very wide. For example, with the help of Windows Media Player, you can not only listen to music from any media, but also compress audio tracks from an audio CD in *mp3 format, create a multimedia library, burn audio CDs from audio line pages and music files. The need to use player programs in music lessons is related to its uniqueness. Easy to control music playback, based on a single principle, having a brightly colored interface; the appearance of listening to music with video effects and its construction is based on the characteristics of the composition. All this allows you to easily manage and control the process of

listening to music (this is a music file or of music fragment makes it easier to search), it is a real-time color video effects which in turn helps to engage the user more and increase the effectiveness of the entire listening process.

Programs for karaoke songs. At the end of the 70s of the 20th century, a popular device called karaoke was invented in Japan. Translated from Japanese, the name means "empty orchestra". The principle of karaoke is very simple: music is played without vocals, the words are displayed on the screen, while the spoken words are rhythmically separated, and the vocal line is performed on any musical instrument.

PC-based karaoke offers truly limitless possibilities for the performer. This theme is a large selection of computer software. For example, such software products as Vocal Jam, GalaKar, Vanbasco's karaoke player and others are considered. The first part of these programs has a wide range of possibilities that enrich the performance process: the ability to evaluate intonation, record vocals, improve sound, quick search for songs, solfeggio course, exercises for reading notes.

Any multimedia computer with even lower parameters (i.e. sound card, CD or DVD drives, DirectX compatible) can still be a powerful tool for karaoke songs. There are free downloads of songs and other vocal compositions for playing karaoke songs from various sites. Another interesting feature of computer karaoke is the KarMaker program, with the help of which you can write a song independently.

When using computer karaoke, using the capabilities of sound cards, you can add volume, space ("concert hall", "stadium", "auditorium"), chorus effects, echo, etc., slightly transpose the volume of the entire phonogram and change the general tempos. Having makes the songs very interesting.

Using a computer to sing karaoke, the performer can easily burn the result of his performance to CDs and other media, listen to it, evaluate its quality "from the outside", etc.

The undoubted advantages of karaoke are the implementation of the motivational principle "low-cost quality result in a short time", a large selection of songs and devices for their performance. It is recommended to use karaoke songs in music lessons in secondary schools.

Video recording allows you to significantly expand the repertoire of performed songs, at the same time, school students master such activities as writing words in a text editor on a computer and memorizing words. In addition, an auxiliary tone that controls any musical instrument helps to simplify and activate the

process of engaging school students in vocal performance. Flexible tempo settings and, most importantly, tonalities allow the teacher to fully focus on working with the student choir. In addition, higher educational institutions do not have developed methods for using these tools in music lessons in the field of music education. Despite the widespread use of phonograms, the possibility of relying on video sequences with lyrics (this is the main distinguishing feature of karaoke) is almost never used, even if school music teachers use "minuses" in practice.

Musical encyclopedias. Several groups of programs, each with its own characteristics. The most interesting part of them: "Encyclopedia of classical music", "Encyclopedia of famous music of Cyril and Methodius", "Big encyclopedia of Cyril and Methodius".

For example, in programs such as Lenny's MusicTools, which is devoted to the study of sheet music and implemented in the form of a game, the student is offered three missions. In the first mission, he is a soldier on Mars and shoots down flying saucers (indicate which note is played to hit the saucer). In the second mission, he enters a village where happy animals live. According to the results of the first two tasks, the student will have to learn not only to write notes and their names, but also to learn how to place them on the piano keyboard. In the third part of the program, we go to the disco, where the player can create his own show under colorful light beams with special lights of his own musical style, choose to music and artists "DJ" becomes.

Programs for improvisation and musical compositions. There are relatively few programs belonging to this group, and it is appropriate to include DoReMix, DRGN, Microsoft Music Producer, Magix Music Maker.

Thus, based on a brief analysis of the capabilities of the considered musical computer programs, it can be concluded that today's modern computer can be a powerful and useful tool in the pedagogical activity of a music teacher aimed at developing the musical interest of his students. However, in order to actively use modern information technologies, a music teacher must solve the tasks of mastering existing computer music programs and developing new pedagogical technologies of the 21st century based on them.

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